

Readiness, Competence and Difficulty of Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the readiness, competence, and difficulties of 60 public elementary school teachers from five schools in a district of a large division in Central Philippines in implementing the in-person learning modality, serving as a basis for evaluating teacher performance. Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected through a validated four-part, 42-item instrument on readiness and competence and a 10-item scale on difficulties, all demonstrating high reliability (Cronbach alphas: 0.911 for readiness, 0.901 for competence, and 0.851 for difficulties). Frequency, percentage, and mean were used to describe the variables, while the Mann-Whitney U Test at a 0.05 significance level determined differences across groups. Findings revealed no significant differences in teachers' readiness and competence, but significant differences emerged in difficulties encountered when grouped by selected variables. Recommendations emphasized stronger collaboration among school heads, teachers, and parents in elevating concerns to the Department of Education, particularly regarding the need for high-speed internet to support in-person instruction. The study further suggested tapping IT teachers for hands-on computer literacy training, giving additional support to academically struggling learners, addressing prior knowledge gaps, and fostering a positive learning environment through continuous guidance and feedback. Teachers were encouraged to pursue action research, improve assessment practices using clear language and diverse methods, and engage in ongoing professional development and collaboration. Finally, school heads were advised to reinforce punctuality and attendance to strengthen teacher discipline and promote a more efficient and effective learning atmosphere.

Keywords: Instructional competence, in-person learning challenges, Teacher readiness

How to Cite:

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INTRODUCTION

In today's millennial era, teachers are expected to be adaptable, competent, and technologically proficient to effectively manage classrooms and guide advanced learners. Their readiness for in-person learning is assessed through their digital literacy and instructional capabilities, which are crucial as schools transition from remote to face-to-face modalities. Despite these expectations, many teachers face challenges in adjusting to the new setup, requiring continuous support through training, workshops, and tutorials to navigate the evolving demands of the teaching-learning process.

The implementation of DepEd Order No. 34, s. 2022 mandates all public and private schools to fully resume five-day in-person classes starting November 2, 2022, with exceptions only for those using Alternative Modes. This directive underscores the need for teachers to be well-prepared and qualified to uphold academic standards in a post-pandemic educational landscape. As such, professional development initiatives have been intensified to equip educators with the necessary competencies to deliver quality education under the revised modality.

Amid these transitions, the Department of Education continues to provide support to ensure that teachers and school administrators can meet the challenges of in-person learning. The shift from modular distance learning has posed difficulties in maintaining educational quality, but ongoing efforts aim to enhance teacher proficiency and institutional readiness. These measures reflect a broader commitment to sustaining effective education delivery and addressing systemic gaps in teacher preparedness during this critical period.

Therefore, as a public elementary school teacher, readiness in classroom management, curriculum implementation, and learners' participation, their IPCRF-based competencies in knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and assessment and reporting, and their difficulties experienced in the In-person learning modality. Hence, the researcher hopes to find answers to these concerns for improving the schools' In-person learning modality used.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the levels of readiness, competence, and difficulties of Public Elementary School Teachers in the In-person learning modality in a District of a large Division of Central Philippines for the school year 2022-2023 based on an evaluation of the Teachers' Performance. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the level of readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in the implementation of the in-person learning modality in the area of classroom management, curriculum implementation, learners' participation; 2) the level of competence of Public Elementary School Teachers in the implementation of the in-person learning modality according to the area of knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, assessment and reporting; 3) the difficulties of Public Elementary School Teachers in the implementation of the in-person learning modality; 4) the significant difference in the level of readiness of Public School Elementary Teachers in the implementation of the in-person learning modality when grouped and compared to the aforementioned variables; 5) the significant difference in the level of competence encountered by the Public School Elementary Teachers in the implementation of the in-person learning modality when grouped and compared to the aforementioned variables; and 6) the significant difference in the level of difficulty of the Public Elementary School Teachers in implementing the in-person learning modality when grouped and compared to the aforementioned variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers primarily conducted lessons through face-to-face lectures, interactive activities, and hands-on training that allowed immediate feedback and close supervision. This traditional setup fostered strong teacher-student relationships and direct engagement in learning. However, the sudden onset of the pandemic disrupted this structure and forced a rapid transition to online, modular, and blended learning modalities, leaving both educators and students unprepared and struggling to cope with economic, emotional, and educational challenges (Hermosa, Musico, & Largo, 2022). Despite these obstacles, teachers demonstrated a willingness to adapt to remote teaching, even though many lacked the necessary facilities, equipment, and training (Alea et al., 2020). School leaders generally expressed trust in teachers' capacity to integrate digital tools effectively (Moreno & Gortazar, 2020), while studies also found educators to be competent in multimodal instruction, showing enthusiasm and fostering positive student relationships that enhance learning (Herrera & Janer, 2021; Gonzales, 2016). To improve access to education, several scholars have recommended strengthening internet connectivity and fostering collaboration between the Departments of Education, Energy, and Information and Communications Technology (Agayon et al., 2022). Teacher competence—encompassing teaching effectiveness, professional development, and community engagement—remains central to educational success, highlighting the need for ongoing support and continuous training (Luistro, 2016; Lagrio, 2019).

The shift from in-person to online learning during the pandemic posed significant challenges for both teachers and students, many of whom were unfamiliar with the demands of distance education despite their exposure to technology. Naidu (2020) and

Mishra et al. (2020) explained that the crisis compelled educators to rethink traditional pedagogical approaches and adapt to digital platforms, often for the first time. The outcomes of this shift were mixed: Rouadi and Anouti (2020) reported that online teaching was most successful when teachers employed diverse strategies, sustained communication, and promoted active participation, while Hansson (2021) noted that insufficient preparedness among educators contributed to widespread instructional difficulties. Moreover, Vahey and Vanides (2020) highlighted that inequalities in digital literacy and technology access widened existing educational gaps, particularly in underprivileged communities. Studies by Siri et al. (2020) and Gezer (2018) further linked teaching effectiveness to professional competence and adaptability to evolving educational philosophies. In rural areas, poor internet connectivity and the lack of technological devices severely hindered students' participation, and the absence of hands-on materials limited the teaching of practical subjects. As Fregni and Biba (2020) observed, the lack of direct teacher-student interaction also led to disengagement and passive learning, emphasizing the ongoing struggle to replicate meaningful and equitable learning experiences in virtual classrooms.

In implementing distance learning, teachers faced numerous challenges that complicated their ability to deliver effective instruction. They struggled with time management, unclear communication channels, and delayed feedback mechanisms. Managing multiple online responsibilities—such as moderating discussions, uploading materials, and responding to messages—made it difficult for teachers to balance their workload. Unlike traditional classroom interactions that allow for immediate responses, online communication was often hampered by technical difficulties, including poor internet connectivity and audio issues, making it challenging for teachers to assess and address students' needs. Providing timely and constructive feedback also became difficult, leading to student confusion and lower academic performance (National University, 2022). The Philippines' notoriously slow and unreliable internet, which ranked among the lowest globally in speed and affordability (Asquire Philippines, 2020), further compounded these issues. Although the Department of Education (DepEd) acknowledged that connectivity problems were largely beyond its control, Undersecretary Annalyn Sevilla emphasized the need for teachers and staff to continue adapting to ensure uninterrupted learning amid these limitations (Malipot, 2020).

To mitigate these challenges, DepEd implemented the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) to guide schools in maintaining educational delivery while ensuring the health and safety of learners and staff during the pandemic (Luz, 2020; Eagle News, 2021). The plan served as a framework for schools to develop localized School Improvement Plans that addressed their specific needs and available learning platforms. While many teachers expressed readiness and dedication to their roles, the Teachers' Dignity Coalition emphasized the need for additional preparation time to guarantee both safety and instructional quality (Malipot, 2020). Laguna (2020) stressed that educators must embrace technology and overcome barriers such as limited resources and unstable connectivity. To uphold educational quality, DepEd, through the Teachers Education Council (2017) and DepEd Order No. 35 s. 2016, highlighted the need to strengthen teacher competencies through continuous professional development programs. UNESCO (2014) similarly emphasized that effective teaching requires mastery of subject content, strategic instruction, formative assessment, and professional ethics—all critical components for fostering meaningful and sustained learning in a rapidly evolving educational context.

Despite these systemic efforts, teachers themselves demonstrated remarkable adaptability and resilience amid the crisis. Many employed creative coping strategies to sustain quality instruction despite resource limitations (Agayon, Agayon, & Pentang, 2022). The abrupt shift to remote learning tested their flexibility, compelling them to innovate and participate in training while managing technical, time management, and communication challenges (Cardullo et al., 2021; Laguna, 2020). Collaboration among teachers, parents, and school administrators emerged as an essential mechanism for tracking student progress and ensuring accountability (Herrera & Janer, 2021). However, differences in parents' educational attainment and socioeconomic conditions also affected learners' support and academic outcomes (Manlangit, Paglumotan, & Saperia, 2020). While teachers generally maintained a positive outlook, they still grappled with issues such as unstable internet access, heavy workloads, and limited time for self-care (Borrore & Alva, 2022; Derya, 2022). Studies emphasized that continuous feedback, student engagement, and intervention programs are critical in addressing these challenges and reinforcing teachers' professional growth (Pentang, 2022; Yambot, Vidal, & Ayro, 2023). Collectively, these findings highlight the need for ongoing professional development, institutional support, and collaboration to ensure instructional quality and effective leadership during educational crises (Alanano, Dejito, & Bautista, 2025).

Research also underscores that learner faced numerous difficulties in adapting to online education, including issues with language proficiency, isolation, low instructor motivation, and suboptimal course design (Karkar-Esperat, 2018). Mahlangu (2018) noted that while technological advancements have introduced opportunities for flexible and accessible learning, they have also created challenges related to engagement and equity, especially in practice-based disciplines such as laboratory sciences. The OECD (2019) emphasized the need to enhance classroom assessment practices, as reliance on limited testing formats—such as multiple-choice exams—restricts opportunities for formative assessment and deeper learning. Effective assessment enables teachers to monitor progress and adjust instruction to diverse student needs. During the pandemic, parental involvement became increasingly vital, as studies in Malaysia (Pek & Mee Mee, 2020) showed that active parental engagement positively affected children's academic outcomes. Similarly, research in Chile by Lara and Saracostti (2019) revealed that varying levels of parental

involvement significantly influenced students' performance, reinforcing global evidence that consistent parental support enhances learning success.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

A descriptive research design was utilized to answer the levels of readiness, competency, and difficulties encountered by public elementary school teachers in a District of a large Division of Central Philippines in implementing the in-person learning modality for the school year 2022-2023. It can use various research methods to investigate one or more variables.

According to McCombes (2020), descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions. A descriptive research design can use various research methods to investigate one or more variables.

A descriptive research design is vital to this present study in providing facts and scientific judgment in determining the levels of readiness, competency, and difficulties encountered by public elementary school teachers in implementing an in-person learning modality. Also, this design is appropriate for the study as it projects the present situation and determines the prevailing issues that adequately and accurately help interpret the data.

Study Respondents

The respondents of this study consisted of sixty (60) teachers from six (6) schools within a district of a large division in Central Philippines during the school year 2022–2023. The selection of participants employed purposive sampling, a non-probability technique in which researchers use their judgment in choosing respondents who can provide relevant information (Alchemer, 2022). The respondents were distributed as follows: School A – 10 (16.67%), School B – 10 (16.67%), School C – 8 (13.33%), School D – 9 (15%), School E – 8 (13.33%), and School F – 15 (25%), totaling sixty (60) teachers or 100% of the sample population.

Instruments

A teacher-made questionnaire composed of four parts with a total of 42 items—7 items per area on readiness and competency, and 10 items on teachers' difficulties—was utilized to gather data from teachers in five elementary schools within a district of a large division in Central Philippines. Part 1 covered respondents' demographic profiles, while Part 2 assessed teachers' readiness in classroom management, curriculum implementation, and learner participation. Part 3 measured competency in knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, and assessment and reporting, and Part 4 identified the difficulties experienced during the implementation of in-person learning. A five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (almost never) to 5 (always) was used for responses. The instrument underwent face and content validation by five experts in administration and supervision, all with Doctor of Education degrees from Negros Oriental, following the criteria of Good and Scates, resulting in an excellent overall validity rating with a mean score of 4.74. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, with values of 0.911 for readiness, 0.901 for competency, and 0.851 for difficulties—indicating excellent to good internal consistency (Middleton, 2022; Taber, 2017).

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering the desired data, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Negros Occidental. When given permission, the researcher immediately coordinated with the Public School District Supervisor and school principals of District 1 of a large Division of Central Philippines and administered the survey questionnaires to all the respondents identified, and the same were retrieved for encoding and tabulation. Likewise, the gathered data were computed using MS Excel and SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences).

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in classroom management, curriculum implementation, and learners' participation.

Objective No. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of competence of Public Elementary School Teachers when grouped according to knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, and assessment and reporting.

Objective No. 3 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of difficulties encountered by Public Elementary School Teachers.

Objective No. 4 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine the significant difference in the level of readiness of Public School Elementary Teachers when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 5 also used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine the significant difference in the level of competence encountered by the Public School Elementary Teachers when they are grouped and compared to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 again used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine the significant difference in the level of difficulties of Public Elementary School Teachers when they are grouped and compared to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

In-person learning modality is the traditional mode of teaching now that the Department of Education was allowed to open its doors in the educational institution to welcome learners back into the classroom. The related research literature proves that teachers have undergone many trials to reach this point after almost three years of the pandemic and are still adjusting. The teachers' level of readiness, competence, and difficulties were assessed based on the areas stated in the research instrument. Aside from teachers' volunteerism, the intention to help by answering the questionnaire was also given consent. The distribution of the research instrument was done face-to-face. Since the study's respondents are teachers, data collection was prepared at the convenience of the respondents, and within at least two weeks, the researcher gathered and started tallying. To encourage open dialogue with the respondents, the researcher also made herself available to cater to the questions raised by the respondents. The researcher assured confidentiality and integrity, and adequately discarding the instruments was done after the finality of this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Level of Readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Classroom Management

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I am ready with the in-person delivery when ...</i>		
1. the classrooms are physically ready for the influx of learners.	4.80	Very High Level
2. there is a high-speed internet in school for online assisted learning.	3.12	Moderate Level
3. learners can feel a positive and inclusive classroom environment.	4.40	High Level
4. my learners come to class behave and observes classroom discipline.	4.27	High Level
5. learners are adjusted to the shift of learning modality.	4.25	High Level
6. the materials for learning are available anytime for distribution.	4.38	High Level
7. my work performance shows an outstanding result.	4.45	High Level
Overall Mean	4.24	High Level

Table 1 shows that the overall mean level of readiness of public elementary school teachers in classroom management for in-person learning was 4.24, interpreted as a “high level.” The highest-rated item ($M = 4.80$) indicated that teachers felt most prepared when classrooms were physically ready for learners, while the lowest-rated item ($M = 3.12$) reflected moderate readiness due to limited access to high-speed internet for online-assisted learning. These results suggest that while teachers are confident in managing physical classroom conditions, there remains a pressing need for improved internet connectivity to support digital integration in teaching. This finding aligns with Verde and Valero (2019), who emphasized that educators have had to adapt to new instructional methods and digital tools to meet the evolving demands of education in the modern era.

Table 2

Level of Readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Curriculum Implementation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I feel that I am ready in the implementation of the curriculum because ...</i>		
1. I find no problem or issues in using it.	4.43	High Level
2. I am quick to respond to any sudden shift of technology related tasks (i.e. printing, searching, etc.)	4.12	High Level
3. I am able to attend to any online related meetings (i.e. webinars. Zoom meetings, etc.).	4.58	Very High Level
4. my co-teachers asks for my assistance to help them with their “tech-needs.”	4.03	High Level
5. I am given importance in presentations and other related situations.	4.23	High Level
6. pedagogical and social competence are achieved.	4.35	High Level
7. professional and personal competence are met.	4.35	High Level
Overall Mean	4.30	High Level

Table 2 shows that the overall mean level of readiness of public elementary school teachers in curriculum implementation was 4.30, interpreted as a “high level.” The highest-rated item ($M = 4.58$) indicated that teachers felt very ready to implement the curriculum through participation in online meetings and webinars, while the lowest-rated item ($M = 4.03$) suggested a need for greater support in collaboration and technology use. These results imply that while teachers are confident in implementing the curriculum, they still require additional training and assistance with technological tools to enhance instructional delivery. This finding contrasts with Evans (2021), who emphasized that educational technology should empower teachers and simplify their work, highlighting the need for proper training to maximize its potential in classroom practice.

Table 3

Level of Readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Learners' Participation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I feel that my learners are ready for in-person learning when they ...</i>		
1. come early to school to attend to their class.	4.73	Very High Level
2. are excited in answering to classroom discussion.	4.62	Very High Level

3.	can independently answer their performance tasks.	4.35	High Level
4.	collaborate with their classmates in the learning process.	4.43	High Level
5.	are motivated to come to school every day.	4.68	Very High Level
6.	are open and ready for change.	4.45	High Level
7.	are interested in every lesson and tasks given.	4.60	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.55	Very High Level

Table 3 indicates that the overall mean level of readiness of public elementary school teachers in terms of learners' participation was 4.55, interpreted as a "very high level." The highest-rated item ($M = 4.73$) showed that teachers believed learners were ready for in-person learning when they arrived early for class, while the lowest-rated item ($M = 4.35$) suggested that learners were less prepared to work independently on performance tasks. This implies that although students demonstrate discipline and willingness to attend classes, they still need support in developing independent learning skills. Teachers, therefore, require continuous training in technology integration and personalized learning approaches to address varying learner needs. This aligns with Raudys (2021), who emphasized that personalized learning enables teachers to adapt instruction to individual students' abilities, fostering engagement and academic growth.

Table 4

Level of Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Knowledge and Pedagogy

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I feel that I am competent in the content knowledge and pedagogy since ...</i>		
1. I apply the knowledge of the different content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.95	Very High Level
2. I apply the different teaching strategies to develop and expand critical and creative thinking.	4.82	Very High Level
3. I apply the higher order thinking skills in giving exams.	4.88	Very High Level
4. I believe I am proficient in the use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning.	4.63	Very High Level
5. I built strong relationship with parents and guardian and the wider school community.	4.75	Very High Level
6. I see that my learners' behavior changed for the better.	4.57	Very High Level
7. I was able to meet the objectives of the lessons I teach.	4.85	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.78	Very High Level

Table 4 reveals that the overall mean level of competence of public elementary school teachers in knowledge and pedagogy was 4.78, interpreted as a "very high level." The highest-rated item ($M = 4.95$) indicated that teachers felt highly competent in applying knowledge across different curriculum areas, while the lowest-rated item ($M = 4.57$) reflected lesser confidence in influencing positive changes in learners' behavior. This suggests that although teachers are strong in content knowledge and pedagogy, they recognize the need to enhance strategies that help learners better understand lessons and work independently. This finding aligns with Sieck (2021), who emphasized that information-seeking and questioning skills are key competencies that significantly contribute to effective job performance and continuous improvement.

Table 5

Level of Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Learning Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I feel that I am competent in my learning environment when ...</i>		
1.the school programs and activities were actively participated.	4.67	Very High Level
2.I able to generally use ICT to facilitate the teaching-learning process.	4.38	High Level
3.I believe that I was able to retool and follow-up the literacy and numeracy needs of my struggling learners.	4.58	Very High Level
4.I have improved my professional status through continuing education and in doing my action research.	3.92	High Level
5.I was able to improve the learners' performance through project-based approach.	4.33	High Level
6.instructional competencies were met.	4.37	High Level
7.the ability to scaffold learning based on students' current levels of understanding are obtained.	4.43	High Level
Overall Mean	4.38	High Level

Table 5 shows that the overall mean level of competence of public elementary school teachers in the area of learning environment was 4.38, interpreted as a “high level.” The highest-rated item (M = 4.67) indicated strong competence when teachers and students actively participated in school programs and activities, while the lowest-rated item (M = 3.92) reflected a need for improvement in professional growth through continuing education and action research. These findings suggest that while teachers are confident in managing interactive and engaging environments, they require stronger motivation and institutional support to pursue research and professional development. This aligns with Siri et al. (2020) and Gezer (2018), who emphasized that teachers' competence is influenced by their knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and that professional growth plays a crucial role in sustaining educational quality.

Table 6

Level of Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Assessment and Reporting

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I feel that I am competent when...</i>		
1. areas in the diagnostic assessment are met in the post-assessment of learners.	4.43	High Level
2. formative assessment of learners are high as it is a great factor in giving grades.	4.33	High Level
3. summative assessment results are high, which affects the entire grading system.	4.27	High Level
4. I was able to give formative assessments and provide timely formative feedback.	4.43	High Level
5. I accomplished my year end reports and complied my year end IPCR, MOV and RPMS performance review.	4.55	Very High Level
6. frequent assessment results to evaluate teachers' effectiveness in teaching.	4.32	High Level

7. the teaching-learning process in school showed great importance.	4.53	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.41	High Level

Table 6 shows that the overall mean level of competence of public elementary school teachers in assessment and reporting was 4.41, interpreted as a “high level.” The highest-rated item ($M = 4.55$) indicated strong competence in completing year-end reports and performance reviews, while the lowest-rated item ($M = 4.27$) revealed concern over low summative assessment results affecting the grading system. This suggests that while teachers are proficient in administrative and reporting tasks, they experience challenges in achieving consistently high student performance outcomes, highlighting the need to simplify lessons and strengthen assessment practices. This finding contrasts with Agustin (2022), who emphasized that teacher competence is shaped by educational philosophies that prioritize active learner participation to enhance teaching effectiveness and learning outcomes.

Table 7

Level of Difficulties of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Waking up early and prepare for work.	3.77	High Level
2. Travelling to school due to traffic.	3.00	Moderate Level
3. Meeting with parents or guardians for consultation.	3.45	Moderate Level
4. Dealing with tardy learners due to the new adjustments.	3.35	Moderate Level
5. Concerned parents because of their child’s performance.	3.22	Moderate Level
6. No internet connectivity in school for technology-based learning.	3.42	Moderate Level
7. Flexibility and understanding in different learning styles.	3.58	High Level
8. Pressure from school administrators.	3.33	Moderate Level
9. Creating and engaging lesson plans that fit the curriculum.	3.48	Moderate Level
10. Parental roles at home versus Teacher’s Role in school	3.18	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.38	Moderate Level

Table 7 shows that the overall mean level of difficulties experienced by teachers in implementing the in-person learning modality was 3.38, interpreted as a “moderate level.” The highest-rated difficulty ($M = 3.77$) was “waking up early and preparing for work,” while the lowest-rated ($M = 3.00$) was “traveling to school due to traffic.” These findings indicate that while teachers face moderate challenges, particularly related to transportation and daily routines, such difficulties should serve as motivation to adapt positively for the benefit of their learners. This aligns with Çınar’s (2022) study, which also identified transportation issues, including traffic, climate conditions, and travel costs, as common challenges among teachers working in remote or rural schools.

Table 8

Difference in the Level of Readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Classroom Management When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	28.88	402.50	.484	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	31	32.02				
Civil Status	Single	29	30.64	445.50	.952	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	31	30.37				
Length of Service	Shorter	30	31.78	411.50	.567	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	30	29.22				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	28.82	357.50	.609	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	41	31.28				

Table 8 reveals that there were no significant differences in the level of readiness of public elementary school teachers in classroom management when grouped according to age ($U = 402.50, p = 0.484$), civil status ($U = 445.50, p = 0.952$), length of service ($U = 411.50, p = 0.567$), and highest educational attainment ($U = 357.50, p = 0.609$), as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. These results indicate that teachers' readiness in classroom management does not vary across demographic factors, suggesting a consistent level of preparedness among teachers regardless of personal or professional background. This finding aligns with Borreo and Alva (2022), who emphasized that teachers maintain a positive outlook toward their profession and demonstrate readiness to fulfill their responsibilities within the framework of the new normal in education.

Table 9

Difference in the Level of Readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Curriculum Implementation When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	31.41	423.00	.693	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	31	29.65				
Civil Status	Single	29	30.86	439.00	.876	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	31	30.16				
Length of Service	Shorter	30	31.58	417.50	.628	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	30	29.42				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	29.11	363.00	.671	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	41	31.15				

The analysis of Public Elementary School Teachers' readiness in curriculum implementation, based on Mann-Whitney U tests, revealed no significant differences across the variables of age ($U = 423.00, p = 0.693$), civil status ($U = 439.00, p = 0.876$), length of service ($U = 417.50, p = 0.628$), and highest educational attainment ($U = 363.00, p = 0.671$), all exceeding the 0.05

significance level. Consequently, the hypotheses that there are no significant differences in readiness according to these demographic factors were accepted, indicating that teachers' preparedness for implementing the in-person learning modality does not vary with age, civil status, length of service, or educational attainment. Despite potential challenges and perceived unpreparedness among both teachers and students, the continuation of education remains essential, and returning to in-person classes should carefully consider each school's readiness (Hermosa, Musico, & Largo, 2022).

Table 10

Difference in the Level of Readiness of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Learners' Participation When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	33.74	355.50	.157	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	31	27.47				
Civil Status	Single	29	32.36	395.50	.416	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	31	28.76				
Length of Service	Shorter	30	33.05	373.50	.250	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	30	27.95				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	31.16	377.00	.840	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	41	30.20				

The analysis of Public Elementary School Teachers' readiness in implementing the in-person learning modality based on learners' participation revealed no significant differences across age ($U = 355.50$, $p = 0.157$), civil status ($U = 395.50$, $p = 0.416$), length of service ($U = 373.50$, $p = 0.250$), and highest educational attainment ($U = 377.00$, $p = 0.840$), all exceeding the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the hypotheses that there are no significant differences in readiness according to these demographic factors were accepted, indicating that teachers' preparedness in engaging learners does not vary with age, civil status, length of service, or educational attainment. Despite the lack of significant differences, both teachers and students may still face challenges in readiness during this crisis; nevertheless, education must continue, and returning to in-person classes should carefully consider the readiness of schools, students, and parents, requiring thorough preparation (Hermosa, Musico, & Largo, 2022).

Table 11

Difference in the Level of Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Knowledge and Pedagogy When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	32.60	388.50	.336	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	31	28.53				
Civil Status	Single	29	32.55	390.00	.348	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	31	28.58				

Length of Service	Shorter	30	32.57	388.00	.328	Not Significant
	Longer	30	28.43			
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	32.58	350.00	.503	Not Significant
	Higher	41	29.54			

The assessment of Public Elementary School Teachers' competence in Knowledge and Pedagogy for the in-person learning modality, based on Mann-Whitney U tests, showed no significant differences across age ($U = 388.50, p = 0.336$), civil status ($U = 390.00, p = 0.348$), length of service ($U = 388.00, p = 0.328$), and highest educational attainment ($U = 350.00, p = 0.503$), all exceeding the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, the hypotheses that teachers' competence does not vary according to these demographic factors were accepted, indicating uniformity in pedagogical knowledge and skills. Despite the lack of significant differences, Herrera and Janer (2021) note that teachers demonstrate a very satisfactory level of competence in implementing multimodal learning methods, with school leaders rating their performance as excellent, reflecting teachers' enthusiasm and effectiveness in engaging students throughout class sessions.

Table 12

Difference in the Level of Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Learning Environment When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	29.22	412.50	.581	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	31	31.69				
Civil Status	Single	29	31.91	408.50	.541	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	31	29.18				
Length of Service	Shorter	30	31.57	418.00	.634	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	30	29.43				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	26.76	318.50	.256	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	41	32.23				

The analysis of Public Elementary School Teachers' competence in managing the Learning Environment for in-person learning, based on Mann-Whitney U tests, showed no significant differences across age ($U = 412.50, p = 0.581$), civil status ($U = 408.50, p = 0.541$), length of service ($U = 418.00, p = 0.634$), and highest educational attainment ($U = 318.50, p = 0.256$), all exceeding the 0.05 significance level. Accordingly, the hypotheses that teachers' competence does not vary according to these demographic factors were accepted, indicating consistency in their ability to create and manage effective learning environments. This finding aligns with Hermosa, Musico, and Largo (2022), who emphasize that traditional face-to-face teaching, including lectures, interactive activities, and hands-on practicums, has long been central to effective classroom learning.

Table 13

Difference in the Level of Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of the In-Person Learning Modality According to Assessment and Reporting When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	31.26	427.50	.743	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	31	29.79				
Civil Status	Single	29	28.67	396.50	.429	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	31	32.21				
Length of Service	Shorter	30	31.78	411.50	.566	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	30	29.22				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	28.53	352.00	.548	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	41	31.41				

The analysis of Public Elementary School Teachers' competence in Assessment and Reporting for in-person learning showed no significant differences across age ($U = 427.50, p = 0.743$), civil status ($U = 396.50, p = 0.429$), length of service ($U = 411.50, p = 0.566$), and highest educational attainment ($U = 352.00, p = 0.548$), all exceeding the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the hypotheses that teachers' competence does not differ based on these demographic factors were accepted, indicating uniform proficiency in assessment and reporting practices. This finding suggests that teachers are competent in evaluating and documenting student performance regardless of their background, aligning with Raudy's (2021) assertion that educators must employ flexible and personalized learning strategies to effectively address students' varying learning paces and needs.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that most respondents were married and held master's or doctorate degrees, indicating a mature and academically prepared teaching workforce. Teachers demonstrated a high level of readiness and competence in implementing the in-person learning modality, while their level of difficulty was moderate. No significant differences were observed in readiness and competence across variables, but significant differences in difficulties were noted in relation to civil status and length of service. The findings suggest that teachers are generally prepared to handle in-person classes, though challenges remain in internet connectivity, technology use, and learner independence.

It was concluded that schools should enhance ICT support and training, strengthen teacher empowerment and leadership, encourage continued action research, and provide follow-up assessments to balance grading outcomes. Furthermore, addressing teachers' workload and time management challenges was emphasized as essential for maintaining performance and well-being.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations include installing high-speed internet, retraining teachers in technology use, providing remedial instruction for struggling learners, addressing knowledge gaps through formative feedback, sustaining research initiatives, improving assessment practices, and enforcing punctuality to promote discipline and efficiency among teachers.

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Conflict of Interest

We maintain that none of the authors of this paper have a financial obligation or personal relationship with any person(s) or organizations that could inappropriately influence/bias the paper's content. We do not receive funding from any person(s) or organization to carry out this research. Given this, we specifically state that "No Competing interests are at stake and there is No Conflict of Interest" with any person(s) or organizations that could inappropriately influence/bias the content of the paper.

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